
Social Media as a Social Problem in The Dharashiv District: An Analytical Study

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ABSTRACT

This paper guises at the growing effect of social media in Dharashiv district of Maharashtra and how it has become a social issue, they are focused in this study. One the basis of analytical approach, this study explores the social, cultural, and psychological effects of unnecessary and uncontrolled social media use among young age group. The analysis points out major issues like misinformation, cybercrime, mental health problems, and digital addiction, along with their combined effect on local social structures. The paper ends with suggestions for policy changes, awareness programs, and more research.

Keywords: *Social Problem, Social Media, cybercrime, Mental health, Addictions etc.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the use of Social media has becoming the social status in the youth in India. In the age group of 15 to 30, most of the children's as well as youth connected with social media platform. Several report on the internet, appealed that, near about 692 million social media users in 2025, which is around 49.4% of total population of India. This thing shows that Social media has rapidly transformed communication patterns across India, Including Dharashiv District.

There are number of social media platform enclosed all world into village. In India, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp and X become a more popular social media platforms among youth. At present, each and every person spends his time on social media near about 2 to 3 hours for entertainment, communication and contact with friends or relatives. Social Media platforms offer lot of opportunities to connectivity, business, education and information transfer from one to another people. But the black side of social medias are youth become a habitual to social media and make a lot of crimes unknowingly and this is becoming a trap for him. Today or in future, this will be become a major problem due to social Media. As per the Ministry of Home Affairs and National Crime Records

Bureaus, Social media connected crimes in India have near about triplicated from 2020 to 2024, with cases rising from 56,283 to 1,56,938 respectively. This information has shocking to social media users especially for parents as well as society. So, there is need to analytical study on Social Media as a social problem in in Dharashiv District.

Main study focused on to examine social media as a social problem in Dharashiv District by identifying its adverse social costs and analysing their root causes in society. Also, this study has focused on effect on socio-cultural, psychological and economic from social media in Dharashiv District in Maharashtra. For achievement of purpose of this study, 100 samples have been selected form Students, parents & Teacher. The opinion of samples has been collected, analysed and interpreted systematically.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The objectives of the study are as follows,

- To study and identify social problems associated with social media usage especially children's and students.
- To analyse the socio-cultural and psychological effect of social media in Dharashiv district.
- To find patterns of social media consumption among youth and adults
- To provide suggestion for negative effects and promoting responsible use of social media.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

For conducting the study, used empirical research design combining of quantitative and qualitative methodology.

- **Sample size & Sample selection:**

Total 100 samples were selected from Students, Parents and teachers from the Dharashiv District of Maharashtra State. The convenient and multi-stage method was used to sample selection.

- **Data Collection & Analysis Tools**

Data was collected through questionnaires, telephone interviews and observation from the students, parents and teachers. The questionnaires were collected through email and WhatsApp. The social media habits of youth were observed in public places and educational institutions. Based on these tools and techniques, primary data was collected. The quantitative data were analysed using percentage, frequency distribution and mean.

4. SOCIAL MEDIA LANDSCAPE IN DHARASHIV DISTRICT:

A) Demographic Profile of Respondent

Dharashiv District is situated in Marathwada Region of Maharashtra in India. It has 08 talukas i.e. Dharashiv, Tuljapur, Umarga, Kalamb, Paranda, Bhum, Lohara and Washi. For the administration

purposes, it is divided into two sub-divisions from namely Dharashiv Sub-division & Bhum Sub-division.

This study is focus only on social media and its social problems in Dharashiv district. To conduct this study, 100 samples have been selected from Students (45), Parents (35) and Teachers (20).

Table: 01 Age Group of Respondent

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
15-20	24	24%
21-30	23	23%
31-40	25	25%
41-50	21	21%
51+	7	7%
Total	100	100%

Table 01, indicates the age group of respondents which is used Social Media, it shows that, survey samples are concentrated in younger age groups. Total 72% out of 100% of respondents are under 40-year-old and 28% are above 40 age group. It shows that, the high representation of above 40 years age group and main study gets proper information about the social problems due to Social media.

Table: 02 Residence Area of Respondent

Demography	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	38	38%
Urban	62	62%
Total	100	25%

Table 02 show the participation of respondents from urban area (62%) is significantly higher than that from rural areas. This indicates that the more social problems are in the urban societies.

B) Opinion of students

- **Profile of Social Media Users.**

The total 45 students' option has analysed and interpreted for measuring the consumption pattern of Social Media in Dharashiv District.

Table: 03 Social Media Platforms use regularly

Platforms	Frequency	Percentage
WhatsApp	14	31%
Facebook	11	25%
Instagram	5	11%
YouTube	15	33%
Other	0	0
Total	45	100%

Table 03 shows users used pattern of social media. It indicates that, YouTube (33%), WhatsApp (31%) & Facebook (25%) is the high engagement platforms of social media. This data

confirms that the social media consumption pattern of this group is heavily driven by YouTube & WhatsApp, with traditional Facebook platform maintaining a strong, but secondary position.

Table: 04 Consumption Time Period on Social Media

Time Consumption	Frequency	Percentage
<1 Hour	5	11%
1-3 Hours	8	17%
3-5 Hours	25	56%
>5 Hours	7	16%
Total	45	100%
Mean	3.64 Hours	

Table 04 indicates the time spent on social media, the mean time of 3.64 hours is significantly high, indicating that students in Dharashive District. It shows the high average engagement on social media, the majority of students, 60% (51% + 09%), spend 03 to 05 hours on social media daily.

Table: 05 Primary Purpose for using Social Media

Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
1. Entertainment	22	49%
2. News & Information	3	7%
3. Connecting with Friends	14	31%
4. Education	3	7%
5. Following local politics	2	4%
6. Social Movement	1	2%
Total	45	100%

Table 05 indicates primary purpose for using social media, this strongly conclude that, the primary purpose for using social media is Entertainment & Connecting with friends. This imbalance is a crucial finding for understanding the performs potential negative impacts on academic focus and responsibility citizenship.

• **Social & Psychological Impact of Social Media on Students.**

Table 06: Students Opinion on Social & Psychological Impact

Question	1	2	3	Mean
1. Distracts from studies and daily responsibilities	7	12	26	2.42
2. Often feel anxiety or stress when see the achievements or lifestyles of others	21	7	17	1.91
3. Negatively affected on sleep schedule.	2	5	38	2.8
4. Feel more informed about local local issues because of social media.	28	12	5	1.49

(01-Disagree, 02-Nutral, 03-Agree)

Table 06 shows the students’ opinion on social & psychological effects of Social Media. These results are;

- Most respondents (26) agreed that social media distracts them from their responsibilities. The mean of (2.42) is closed to 03 i.e. agree.
- Respondents are generally mixed or neutral as to whether they feel anxiety or street from seeing other lives on social media. The mean of (1.91) is closer to 02 i.e. neutral.
- Most respondents (38) agreed that social media has had a negative impact on their sleep schedule. The mean of (2.80) is closer to 03 i.e. Agree.
- Most respondents disagree (28) that social media makes them feel more informed about local issues. The mean of (1.49) is close to 01 i.e. disagreeing.

C) Opinion of Parents about Social Media.

The opinion of 35 parents has taken and the data has been analysed and interpreted as follows;

Table 07: Observation of Parents about Social Media

Particulars	1	2	3	Mean
1. Amount of time child spends on social media.	1	2	32	2.42
2. Noticed a negative change on child's behaviour	0	0	35	1.91
3. Reduced the quality time - family spends together.	2	5	28	2.80
4. Feel social media helps in promoting the local culture and Marathi language among the youth.	28	5	2	1.49

Table 07 show the Observation of parents about his children’s in Social media platform. It shows that:

- Most of the parents (32) show strong agreement regarding their concern over the amount of time their child spends using social media in Dharashiv District..
- All of the parents (35) agreement among parents that excessive social media use has caused a negative change in their child's behaviour.
- Most of the parent (28) agree that social media has reduced the amount of quality time their family spends together.
- Most of the parents (28) strongly disagree that social media helps in promoting the social culture and Marathi language among the youth.

Fear of Parents about social Media

Table 8: Biggest Fear regarding social media usage children

Particular	Response	Percept
1. Addiction	28	80%
2. Contact with strangers	12	34%
3. Cyber bullying	17	49%
4. Exposure to inappropriate content	24	69%
5. Distraction from studies	35	100%

The table 08 shows that the risks of social media are widely perceived, with 100% of respondents identifying the risk of distraction from studying, followed by 80% fearing addiction, 69% mentioning exposure to inappropriate content, and 49% expressing concerns about cyber bullying and 34% about contact with strangers.

- **Parents aware this children's about social media usage and safety**

Table 9: Parent response towards discuss social media usage and safety

Response	Frequency	Percept
dally	7	20%
Weekly	5	14%
Monthly	2	6%
Rarely	7	20%
Never	14	40%
Total	35	100%

Table 09 shows that, 60% of parents have discussed social media use and safety with their children (with varying frequency), indicating that most parents are engaged in some level of communication. However, the 40% who never discuss the topic represent a significant communication gap. While this large percentage indicates a lack of awareness, resources, or priority for digital safety, it would be wrong to conclude that this group "doesn't care" about their children's well-being. The data only shows a gap between communication and action, not underlying parental concern.

Mechanism of Controlling the Negative Effects of Social Media.

Table 10: Parent response towards controlling the negative effects of social media on youth

Response	Percept
Parental controls	45%
School-based education	34%
Government regulations	52%
Personal limits set by the child	61%

The table 10 shows a clear preference for personal limits set as the most effective method among parents, with the highest percentage at 61%. This suggests that individuals consider self-regulation and personal responsibility to be the most effective tools. Closely followed, government regulation was also considered highly effective by 52% of respondents, indicating a significant demand for legal oversight. Parental controls received a moderate level of support from 45%. The least preferred of the four options was school-based education, mentioned by 34% of respondents. Overall, the findings show a split opinion, with a slight majority preferring a combination of personal responsibility and external government intervention.

Opinion of Teachers about academic & psychological impact

The opinion of 20 parents has taken and the data has been analysed and interpreted as follows;

Table 11: Opinion of Teachers about academic & Psychological impact of social media on Students (01-Disagree, 02- Neutral, 03-Agree)

Opinion	1	2	3	Mean
1. Social media affects students' academic concentration in class	0	2	18	2.9
2. Students used to use social media during school hours.	0	1	19	2.95
3. Students use social media for academic materials and studies.	1	7	12	2.55

Table 11 indicates that, almost all the teachers strongly opinion (mean between =2.90-2.95) that social media has a negative impact on student’s concentration and is used during school hours. While teachers noted that there is slightly lower consensus that students use it for academic purposes

Table 12: Opinion of Teachers about Social problem & responsible use

Opinion	Yes	No
1. Deal with cases of cyber bullying or social media-related conflicts among students	12 (60%)	8 (40%)
2. Adequate skills in identifying Fake News or Misinformation.	02 (10%)	18 (90%)
3. Organising program or workshop on Digital Literacy and Responsible Social Media Use.	12 (60%)	8 (40%)

Table 12 shows that, 60% of teachers reported noticing incidents of cyber bullying or social media-related conflicts among students. Furthermore, a very high percentage (90%) of teachers

observed that students lacked the necessary skills to identify fake news or misinformation. Finally, 60% of teachers confirmed that their institution had organized programs related to digital literacy and responsible social media use.

5. KEY FINDING & SUGGESTION

Key Finding:

a) Usage Patterns

- 72% of respondents are under 40 year old.
- 62% respondents in urban area which is significantly higher than rural area.

b) Opinion of Students

- YouTube (33%), WhatsApp (31%) & Facebook (25%) regularly used by students.
- **56%** of students use social media for more than 3-5 hours daily.
- 49% of students used social media for Entertainment and 31% for connecting with friends.
- 58% of students agreed that the social media distracts them from their responsibilities.
- 38% of students agreed that they feel anxiety or stress when see the achievements or lifestyles of others on social media.
- 84% of students noticed that, social media has negatively effect on sleep schedule.
- Only 04% students feel more informed about local issues because of social media.

c) Opinion of Parents

- 91% of parents noticed that the amount of time children's spends on social media.
- 100% of parents noticed that negative change on children's behaviours because of social media.
- 80% of parents noticed that social media has reduced the quality time-family spends together.
- Only 06% parents opinion that social media helps in promoting the local culture and Marathi language among the youth.
- 100% of parent's social media distracting from studies to children's & 80% of parents has a fear of addiction of their childe due to social media.
- 40% of parents never discuss the topic on social media usage and safety.
- 61% of parents suggested that, personal limits set by the child for use of social media and 52% of parents go with government need to upgrade the government regulations and 45% of parents, parental controls is most important to control the social media use among chiliads.

d) Opinion of Teachers.

- Almost all the teacher's opinion that social media has a negative impact on student's concentration and it's used during school hours.
- 60% of teachers reported noticing incidents of cyber bullying or social media-related conflicts among students.
- 90% of teachers observed that students lacked the necessary skills to identify fake news or misinformation.
- 60% of teachers confirmed that their institution has organized programs related to digital literacy and responsible social media use.

Recommendations:

a) Framed Restriction Policy: the government need to frame usage restriction policies for users. If the used restriction policy is used for a maximum of one hour a day, users will use social media as per their requirement. .

b) Digital Literacy Programs: Digital literacy programs should be organized in schools and colleges to promote safe use of social media. These institutions should also start training on how to use social media safely.

c) Distract the students through physical games: Schools and colleges should regularly organise physical games to distract the students from social media. And parents should also motivate their children to participate in games.

d) Training to the parents & Teachers: Most parents as well as teachers are not aware of effect of social media on children on psychology, behaviour changes, cyber security and cyber bullying, hence there is need to organize awareness campaigns for parents as well as to teachers.

e) Strengthening Cyber security Measures: Local law enforcement agencies should conduct cybercrime awareness workshops and improve reporting mechanisms.

f) Mental Health Awareness: Counselling services and helplines should be promoted to overcome addiction and emotional strain. There is also a need to organize mental health campaigns in schools and colleges.

g) Community Engagement: NGOs and local leaders should organize community engagement programs to promote dialogue on ethical digital behavior.

h) Policy Interventions: Government bodies should implement strict measures against misinformation and promote safe internet practices.

i) Restricted on Misinformation and fake news: the government should focus on policies on misinformation and fake news on social media. If users do not follow the rules, there should be restrictions on the use of social media for a specific period of time.

6. CONCLUSION:

Social media has become the most popular and user-friendly platform in Dharashiv district. But on the contrary, social media has become a social problem. Most of the users use social media for entertainment, which means that social and cultural values are deteriorating in children. Also, most of the students feel the social and psychological impact of social media, such as distraction from studies and daily responsibilities, negative impact on sleep schedule, etc.

Parents and teachers agreed that social media has a negative impact on their children. They have the biggest fear of addiction, contact with strangers, cyber bullying and distraction from studies, etc. This can create insecurity in the lives of children. The government should focus on social media related to the problems faced in the social sector and formulate appropriate policies.

7. FUTURE RESEARCH:

The scope of future studies in this area is controversial. The areas identified in the study are:

- a) Social Media as a social problem in Maharashtra as well as in India
- b) Impact of vernacular Misinformation on social harmony and civic participation in Maharashtra districts
- c) Social Media and Youth Mental Health
- d) Social Media and its major problems

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